

ACCOUNTING AND AUDITING OF ELECTRONIC MONEY IN BANKS

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Abstract. A payment system (hereinafter referred to as the "PS") is a set of relations that ensure the implementation of payments through the interaction of (1) the PS operator, (2) the PS participant and (3) payment organizations through the application of (a) procedures, (b) infrastructure and (c) rules of the payment system established by the PS operator. Uzcard, Humo and Upay are currently national payment systems.

Key words: bank, accounting, electronic money, payment system.

Introduction

The PS operator is a legal entity (including a commercial bank) that carries out activities to ensure the functioning of the payment system on the territory of the Republic of Uzbekistan (hereinafter referred to as "RUz") and has received a license to operate a PS operator. It is worth noting that the bank's license for financial transactions (banking activities) does not cover this activity and therefore a commercial bank also needs to obtain the above-mentioned license of the PS operator. Data on such organizations are entered into the Register of Payment Organizations, which is maintained by the Central Bank of the Republic of Uzbekistan (hereinafter referred to as the "Central Bank"). This Registry is not publicly available.

The following national operators ensure the operation of the largest PS on the territory of the Republic of Uzbekistan:

LLC "Unified Republican Processing Center" (Uzcard), established on the basis of and performing the tasks established by the PCM of 24.09.2004 No. 445 and Presidential Decree of 03.08.2006 No. PP-433;

LLC "National Interbank Processing Center" (Humo), established on the basis of and performing the tasks established by Presidential Decree No. PP-3945 dated 19.09.2018.

Member of the PS

The participants of the PS are banks that carry out settlements and have concluded an agreement with the operator of the PS on participation in the payment system. The order of interaction of the participants of the PS with the operator of the PS is defined in the rules of the PS. For example, the Rules of the Humo payment system can be found at the following link: <https://humocard.uz/ru/banks/normative-documents>.

Payment organization

A payment organization means a legal entity that is not a bank, which is authorized to carry out activities for the provision of payment services. This type of activity is licensed. The licensor is the Central Bank. A payment organization can carry out its activities as a payment service provider after obtaining a license.

Payment organizations are not entitled to engage in activities unrelated to the provision of payment services, except for the following activities:

advertising, marketing, consulting and information services;

development, adaptation, modification, technical support of software;

services related to the use of information and communication technologies, including information technology services, data processing and transmission services, creation and use of databases and information resources;

creation and security of information systems and networks;

development and implementation of cryptographic information protection tools;

microfinance services.

Banks and payment organizations have the right to provide payment services to users of payment services through a payment agent and a payment subagent.

According to the Register on the territory of the Republic of Uzbekistan , the following payment organizations carry out activities:

LLC "Slick" (Slick);

LLC "BRIO GROUP" (Oson);

INSPIRED LLC (Payme);

National Innovative Payment Technologies LLC (Paymo);

PAYBOX LLC (Paybox);

LLC "Maroqand" (Upay).

2.2. Types of PS

PS are divided into (1) significant payment systems and (2) other payment systems. The Central Bank classifies the PS as a significant payment system if:

its uninterrupted operation contributes to the stable functioning of the payment services market of the Republic of Uzbekistan;

and stops (failures) in its operation may lead to risks in the payment services market of the Republic of Uzbekistan; if it

occupies a share of the payment services market above the value set by the Central Bank for this market; and (or) if through the PS

payments are made on the territory of the Republic of Uzbekistan during the year in the amount of at least the indicators set by the Central Bank.

Payment systems that do not fall under the criteria described above belong to other payment systems. It should also be noted that the above threshold values have not yet been determined.

Payment Service Providers

Payment service providers are:

Central Bank;

cans;

payment organizations;

payment agents;

payment subagents.

Payment agents are understood as legal entities that are not banks that have concluded an agency agreement with a bank or a payment organization for the provision of payment services. In turn, a payment subagent means a legal entity that is not a bank, or an individual entrepreneur who has concluded a subagent agreement with a payment agent for the provision of payment services.

Payment services

It is prohibited to provide payment services without a license from the Central Bank. Only payment agents and subagents can operate without a license. According to Article 14 of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. ZRU-578, the following services relate to payment services:

accepting and making payments using a bank account;

accepting cash for crediting to bank accounts and without opening an account;

issuance, repayment and sale of electronic money;

issuance and sale of bank cards;

acceptance and processing of payments made using electronic money;

processing payments in electronic form and transmitting the necessary information to the bank for making a payment or accepting funds for these payments;

acceptance and implementation of money transfers through money transfer systems.

Payment services do not include services for:

transfer of cash by the person making the payment to the person to whom the payer has obligations performed without the participation of the payment service provider;

collection of banknotes, coins and valuables;

carrying out exchange operations with cash foreign currency without opening a bank account;

ensuring information, communication and technological interaction between the beneficiary and the payment service provider when the latter makes money transfers in favor of the beneficiary on accepted payments without the participation of third parties.

Terms of payment services

When providing payment services, the payment service provider ensures compliance with the following conditions:

conducting proper verification and identification of the user of payment services in accordance with AML/CFT legislation (due diligence);

the presence in the payment document of the details of the payer and the beneficiary provided for by the AML/CFT legislation, except in cases when the payment organization provides services for accepting cash for making a payment without opening a bank account by the payer;

ensuring the safety of information allowing identification of the payer and (or) beneficiary for at least five years after the provision of payment services;

take the necessary legal, organizational and technical measures to protect the identification means of the user of payment services.

The payment service provider, after providing the payment service, provides the payment service user with a document confirming the fact of providing payment services, on paper or in electronic form.

Payment system operators and payment service providers ensure the confidentiality of the information they receive when providing payment services and do not allow their disclosure to third parties, except in cases provided for by the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Banking Secrecy".

Contractual relations in the system and in the payment services market

The Law on Payments and Payment Systems with different levels of detail regulates contractual relations between the subjects of the PS. Pointing to the contractual nature of the relationship, the Law, on the one hand, contains only references to the following contracts:

agreement on participation in the payment system

agreement on interaction of payment systems

agreement on settlement service between the bank and the payment organization;

an agreement between the payer and the issuer of electronic payment means.

an agreement between the issuer of electronic payment means and the holder of the electronic payment means.

agreement between the issuer of the bank card and the holder of the bank card.

agreement on the use of a bank card;

the contract between the payment agent and the issuer of electronic money or the operator of the electronic money system;

an agreement between the issuer of electronic money and the owner of electronic money - an individual.

an agreement between the issuer of electronic money and an individual entrepreneur or a legal entity.

an agreement between the issuer of electronic money or the operator of the electronic money system and the owner of electronic money.

if the initiator is a customer of the bank. If the initiator is not a customer of the bank, then the initiator presents the order in accordance with the procedure determined by the Central Bank.

On the other hand , the Law regulates the following contracts with a certain level of detail:

contract for the provision of payment services;

agency or sub-agency contract for the provision of payment services;

agreement on the issue, use and repayment of electronic money;

an agreement between the operator of the electronic money system and the issuer of electronic money.

Electronic money system

Electronic money is the unconditional and irrevocable monetary obligations of the issuer of electronic money, stored in electronic form and accepted as a means of payment in the electronic money system. When paying for goods sold (works and services) on the territory of the Republic of Uzbekistan, only electronic money issued on its territory can be accepted. Acceptance of electronic money by an individual entrepreneur or a legal entity as payment when making a transaction is carried out on the basis of an agreement concluded with the issuer of electronic money or another bank that is a participant in the electronic money system.

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